

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCES AND PLAYABILITY OF CFRP GOLF SHAFTS

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Keywords: *Carbon fiber reinforced polymer, golf shaft, deflection, torque, frequency*

1 Introduction

Composite materials are being widely used as alternatives to metals and other traditional materials because they offer high strength and stiffness to weight ratio, excellent corrosion resistance, and design flexibility. Since carbon fibers were commercially available in 1970s, carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) developments have mainly been driven by high-performance and low-volume production industries like aerospace and sports goods due to high production costs resulting from expensive raw materials and labor intensive fabrication processes [1]. Although the CFRPs have received much recent attention as industrial materials in other industrial sectors such as construction, transportation and medical applications, the sport industry is still one of major end users for CFRP materials.

The CFRPs were introduced in the last decades to the golf industries and the CFRP shafts are widely accepted by amateur and professional players due to their low-weight and high stiffness enabling them to play with more consistent trajectory and longer distance of golf shots to replace wood or metal golf shafts. This study experimentally investigates the effects of carbon fibers on mechanical performance of golf shafts in terms of shaft deflection, degree of torsion and frequency of vibration in addition to playability and durability of golf clubs. In addition, a non-destructive evaluation was performed to identify the internal damage in the golf shaft after air cannon ball tests. The assessment of the shaft performance can provide a valuable testing ground for new carbon fibers and CFRP materials.

2 Experiments

2.1 Carbon fiber properties

Newly developed carbon fibers (A) were kindly provided by A company, and their mechanical properties are given in Table 1 with the Weibull distribution shape parameter for the fiber strength as a function of gauge length. The Weibull distribution parameters are well defined elsewhere [2]. The shape parameter was determined by plotting Eq.1, as shown in Fig. 1.

$$\ln\left[\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-F(x)}\right)\right] = \beta \ln x - \beta \ln \alpha \quad (1)$$

High value of the shape parameter indicates that flaws are evenly distributed throughout the material, whatever they are plentiful or not, and hence strength is nearly independent of the gauge length [3]. The low values indicates that flaws are fewer and less evenly distributed, causing greater scatter in fiber strength. The A carbon fibers show the lower strength and higher modulus with a wider range of the shape parameter (2.7-4.1), compared with those of the B fibers (Toray, T700). The smaller shape parameter in the A fiber indicates a larger scatter of the strength and less evenly distributed flaws, leading to the stronger dependence on gauge length.

2.2 Manufacture of unidirectional preregs

The carbon fibers were used for the manufacture of unidirectional (UD) preregs through the hot-melt prepregging method with epoxy-based resin films. The preregs have nominal resin content of 33 wt. % and area density of 150g/m². The tensile properties of the resultant UD composites are shown in Table 2. To compare the performance of golf shafts between the two different carbon fibers, commercial UD

prepregs (B Company) were purchased and used to make golf shafts.

2.3 Manufacture of golf shaft

The golf shafts were fabricated by the mandrel wrapping of the UD prepregs with the stacking sequence of [45/45/45/45/0/0/0/0], and the shaft tip was further reinforced with four 0° plies. The pre-patterned prepregs were wrapped by heat shrinkage polypropylene tape and cured in a convection oven at 120°C for 2 hours. The cured shafts were polished into the specification and dimension of golf shafts, as shown in Table 3 and Fig.2.

3 Evaluation of mechanical performance of golf shafts

3.1 Deflection

Shaft deflection describes the stiffness or ability to resist bending during swing motion. The deflection is one of critical factors for determining the desired swing position and right impact points of the head in the management for shaft quality [4]. The deflection is measured by hanging a mass of 2.73kg at a distance from the tip of shaft with different span length (SP), as shown in Fig.3. Table 4 shows that the A shafts are stiffer than the B shafts due to the higher modulus of A carbon fibers. Both shafts show the increase in deflection with increasing the span length.

3.2 Frequency

Shaft frequency is expressed as cycles per minutes (CPM) related to the flex of shaft. Flex is generally rated as Extra Stiff (X), Stiff (S), Regular (R), Senior (A) and Ladies (L). If the number of CPM is 280, the flex is defined as 8.0, and likewise the frequency of 260 becomes 6.0. Although there is no standard in the industry, generally, for drivers, R is 5.5 and S is 6.5. The CPM are determined by vibrating the shaft with the shaft tip hung to 205g mass and shaft butt fixed by clamp, as shown in Fig.4. The results of shaft frequency are listed in Table 5, showing that the A shafts display the higher CPM value than that of the B shaft due to the stiffer shafts. The frequency of the vibrations throughout the shaft is related to the bending stiffness. That is in a good agreement with shaft deflection.

3.3 Torque

Shaft torque are represented as the degree of twist and measured by how much a shaft would twist given a certain twisting force of 0.45 kgf, as shown in Fig.5. The shaft torque is related to shaft deflection and flex, all of which work together to control ball trajectory and the hitting point of a golf ball on the head faces. The torque of steel shaft is around 2.0 and the common CFRP shafts have the torque in the range of 3.5 to 5 [5]. In principle, a higher torque shaft will feel more flexible than will a lower torque shaft at the same frequency. Table 6 shows that the A shaft has a lower torque value due to the stiffer carbon fibers, that is consistent with the test results of shaft deflection and frequency.

4 Playability of golf clubs

The utility golf club was manufactured by assembling a shaft and a head (hybrid 19°) for club playability testing. The club testing was carried out by a swing robot (Golf laboratories, San Diego) and a radar ball tracking system (Trackman, Denmark). The club speed, ball trajectory, distance are compared between the two different golf shafts in Table 7. The A shaft clubs show higher forgiveness and longer distance, that can be attributed to the good combination of shaft deflection and frequency. In particular, a stiff low torque of the A shaft can improve ball trajectory and forgiveness with toe and heel hits (drop-off in distance from center hits to off center hits). Fig. 6 shows the testing hit spots in the club head.

5 Durability of golf clubs

The durability of golf club was evaluated by air cannon ball tests. The shaft was fixed at the club grip and the club head was impacted by golf ball at the speed of 50m/s. After the 10,000 ball shots, all the club head faces and shafts had no visual defect and deformation. X-ray computed tomography (CT) was employed to detect the internal damage around the shaft tip. X-ray CT images are shown in Fig. 7. Delamination propagation can be observed in both golf shafts, lengthwise along the shaft. The delamination cracks are located in the compressive stress zone, induced by the shaft bending due to the ball impact. This implies that the interlaminar

fracture might be initiated and propagated by compressive flexural or shear stresses. The delamination pattern of the A shaft is very clear and sharp with a single crack whereas the B shaft has multiple cracks in the diffused larger area. Although both shafts satisfy the durability specification over 10,000 ball hits, the A shaft is found more durable than the B shaft in terms of the delamination toughness.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of carbon fibers with Weibull distribution shape parameters

Carbon fibers	Gauge length [mm]	Modulus [GPa]	Mean Strength [GPa]	Weibull shape parameter
A	10	260	4.1	2.7
	25	255	3.7	2.4
	50	267	3.4	4.1
B	10	233	5.2	3.5
	25	240	4.2	4.0
	50	219	3.5	4.0

Table 2 Mechanical properties of UD composites

Sample	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [GPa]	Fiber vol. fract. [%]
A	140.9	2.2	55
B	126.0	2.5	54

Table 3 Golf shaft specification

Shaft	Length [inch]	Weight [g]	Tip dia. [mm]	Butt dia. [mm]
A	41	64	9.40	15.24
B	41	63	9.40	15.13

Table 4 Shaft deflection

Shaft SP(mm)	Deflection [mm]					
	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3
750	71	71	71	79	75	77
800	80	80	80	85	84	84
850	90	92	90	97	94	97

Table 5 Shaft frequency

Shaft SP(mm)	Frequency [CPM]					
	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3
750	288	287	287	271	274	273
800	270	271	273	255	259	258
850	255	255	257	242	245	242

Table 6 Shaft torque

Shaft SP(mm)	Torque [°]					
	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3
750	4.8	4.8	4.7	4.7	4.9	4.8
800	5.1	5.2	5.1	5.6	5.5	5.9
850	5.5	5.5	5.6	6.3	6.9	6.1

Table 7 Playability of golf clubs

Club	Club speed	X [m]	Y [m]	Z [m]	Total distance
					[m]
A-C	143.1	116.8	25.3	-0.9	198.2
A-R	143.1	111.0	23.7	6.2	193.1
A-L	143.2	108.8	23.1	-10.7	189.4
B-C	141.2	112.7	31.1	1.2	190.0
B-R	141.4	108.9	27.9	10.6	185.7
B-L	141.2	107.4	28.6	-10.0	181.8

*C: club head center hit, R: 14mm right off center hit (heel), L: 14mm left off center hit (toe), as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.1. Weibull plot for tensile strength of A carbon fibers at gauge length of 10 mm.

Fig.2. Dimension of golf shaft with tip thickness of 5.0 mm and butt thickness of 2.2 mm.

Fig.3. Test methods for shaft deflection.

Fig.4. Test methods for shaft frequency.

Fig.5. Test methods for shaft torque.

Fig.6. Playability evaluation with a swing robot.

(a)

(b)

Fig.7. X-ray CT images; (a) A shaft and (b) B shaft.

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